

STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF THE LIVER IN EXPERIMENTAL CHOLESTASIS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11194595>

Relevance. Cholestasis syndrome is a pathologic process that occurs frequently in the population. According to statistics (WHO) it occurs in 1-2 cases per 10,000 people. Cholestasis occurs predominantly in elderly people. There are many scientific studies on cholestasis, its types, etiology, pathogenesis, clinic and treatment, but scientific studies on morphologic changes in the liver of cholestasis patients cannot be considered sufficient.

This article is devoted to more detailed coverage of some aspects of these problems.

Keywords. Cholestasis syndrome, liver morphology.

Object and methods of research. The object of our scientific study was the liver of 21 adult rabbits of chinchilla breed. From them 7 control and 14 experimental 7 of which with short term (5 days) and 7 on 20 days. For the study of liver slices of experimental animals we used methods of staining slices with hematoxylin-eosin and Van-Gizon.

Results of the study. In short terms (5 days) of experimental cholestasis there was a slight swelling and thickening of the liver capsule of rabbits, that is, the thickness of the liver capsule averaged 10-12 μm or 18-20 μm in the portal zone.

During a short period (5 days) of experimental exposure, there was a slight expansion of the diameter of the interlobular artery, that is, it averaged $8.18 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{m}$. The size of the interlobular vein of rabbits of the control group is $60.50 \pm 1.18 \mu\text{m}$, and on the 5th day of the experiment this index is equal to $65.38 \pm 1.52 \mu\text{m}$. The diameter of the interlobular bile duct of the liver of rabbits averages $16.28 \pm 0.74 \mu\text{m}$, that is, it is significantly dilated in short terms (5 days) of experimental cholestasis.

On the 5th day of experimental cholestasis a significant increase in the diameter of the central vein was found, when in control rabbits it was equal to $76.35 \pm 1.28 \mu\text{m}$, and after the experiment this index amounted to $80.55 \pm 1.64 \mu\text{m}$.

In short terms of experimental cholestasis the size of rabbit liver hepatocytes is $27,46 \pm 0,38 \mu\text{m}$, nuclei - $9,58 \pm 0,16 \mu\text{m}$, when as in rabbits of control group this index is $25,65 \pm 0,30 \mu\text{m}$ and $7,20 \pm 0,18 \mu\text{m}$. The nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio of liver cells is 0.35, whereas in control rabbits, this ratio is 0.31.

In late (20 days) terms of experimental cholestasis morphological changes in the liver of rabbits deepen, that is, there are reactive changes. Focal sclerosis is noted, i.e. the thickness of the capsule was 12-14 microns, and at the portal region of the liver 22-24 microns.

The sizes of blood vessels (interlobular, perilobular) and bile ducts in this period of experiment in the liver of rabbits significantly increased. The diameter of interlobular veins was $68.78 \pm 2.15 \mu\text{m}$, insignificantly increased in comparison with control rabbits.

Conclusion. In late (20 days) terms of experiment the cross section of interlobular bile ducts of liver of rabbits increased in 1,2 times in comparison with control rabbits, diameter of the central vein of liver was also increased. Blood stasis in the blood circulatory system of the liver occurs. Such condition can lead to various degrees of dystrophic, fibrotic and sclerotic changes in the liver.